

Caring Moments at St. Dominic Medical Center in view of Watson's Caring Science

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Abstract

The study aimed to describe the lived experiences of SDMC Registered Nurses, using the existential phenomenological method espoused by Van Manen (2014) in analyzing the experiences.

The experiential themes (first reflection) from textual transcription of 4 Registered Nurses revealed: Nurse S shares, "When I am with the patient, I immerse myself in the totality of patient care". Thus, the theme: Commitment and Compassionate Care. Nurse D verbalized; I have a feeling of satisfaction when I see that the patient loneliness subsides". Thus, the theme: Gratification in Action. Nurse M expressed, "I felt fulfilled when the patient and family treats me as part of the family. Thus, the theme, Patient and Compassionate Nurse equals Family. Nurse C voiced, "When you are equipped with basic information to answer patient's questions rapport is easy to establish". The theme: Cognitive Aspect of Care.

The second reflection describes caring at the core, inner compass of care, nurturing begets belonging and confidence in knowing. The third reflection sums up the details into "Authentic Caring and Rapport as central to relationship. Hence, the gist of the lived experiences outlined that in every Nurse- Patient relationship, there is a caring moment and human interaction.

Keywords: Caring. Caring Moments. Phenomenology. Human Interactions. Watson's Caring Science

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Introduction

Caring moments are quite simple human to human interactions. These interactions have the potential to create a moment of transcendence (healing), (Watson,2013). A caring moment emphasizes the importance of nurse's choice and action to benefit the patient, opening the possibility for healing.

In the evolution of Jean Watson's carative factors to clinical caritas process to caritas literacy and caritas consciousness, shows that over time, we discover profound meaning of caring. Caring as the center of the Nurse-Patient Relationship has been the core of discussion in different researches specifically, Watson's caring science-based interventions which have shown a decrease in patients' emotional strains; increase patients' self-management confidence and emotional well-being, increase nurses' job satisfaction and engagement; improve nursing students' confidence in the clinical performance and the awareness of caring behaviors (Wei and Watson, 2019). Nurse - Patient interaction as an essential element in developing a trusting relationship throughout the hospital stay (and sometimes beyond) can only be possible when grounded with care.

In Watson's Caring Science Institute (2010), caring moment is described to be "present when the nurse and the patient come together in a human-to-human transaction that is meaningful, authentic, intentional, honoring the person, and sharing human experience that expands each person's worldview and spirit leading to new discovery of self and other and new life possibilities". It is in the caring moment that the nurse and the patient realized the value of interconnectedness leads to healing.

Recognizing the caring consciousness, affirms that caring is the most essential element in nurse-patient relationship. This leads to the clarification that among the different concepts and inquiries on caring processes, the most important is the here and now, for and with the patient at that point in time, which is hoped to be the precursor to healing. Healing in this context is not merely the cure of the physical aspect but the holistic approach of care, centering on the mind-body-spirit.

Methodology

The study utilized an existential phenomenological type of research to describe the lived experiences of four nurses of St Dominic Medical Center. The lived experience phenomenology is a science whose purpose is to describe the appearance of things as a lived experience (Ashworth, 2018). It sought to understand the phenomena through collection of rich narrative design (Van Manen, 2014). Phenomenology was chosen to further extract insights, views and experiences, expressed during the interview.

Descriptive Phenomenology was first developed by Husserl, who was primarily interested in the question? What do we know as persons? His philosophy emphasized description of human experience. This study specifically, used Van Manen's method (2014) a combined approach in which the researchers tried to grasp the essential meaning of the experiences being studied. Van Manen's approach involves six activities: (1) turning to the nature of the lived experience; (2) exploring the experience as we live it; (3) reflecting on the essential themes; (4) describing the phenomenon through the art of writing and rewriting; (5) maintaining a strong relation to the phenomenon; (6) balancing the research context by considering parts and whole.

On the other hand, the schematization process consists of four reflections. The first reflection consists of textual transcription and individual theme. The second reflection includes composite themes arising from co-researcher's experiences. Interlace the theme on their common ground as the third reflection. The vivid gist of the picture as eidetic insight as the fourth reflection (Van Manen, 2014).

A qualitative design in an existential phenomenological approach was chosen to describe the lived experiences of the nurses in purposive sampling that met the following criteria: (1) currently employed at St. Dominic Medical Center; (2) at least three years of experience in various wards of the said institution; (3) male or female Filipino Nurses and (4) willing to share their experiences to conceptualize the phenomenon under study.

The researchers sought permission by asking the co-researchers to sign the informed consent form to ensure understanding of the purpose and significance of the study. Data were gathered through an in-depth interview with each of informant in September 2018. The interview was conducted face to face at pre-arranged dates and time which approximately lasted for 60 minutes. The interview was continued until no new theme emerged or until the data saturation was obtained. The Research Ethics Committee conducted a full-blown review of the research and granted an approval to conduct and complete the study.

Results and Discussion

The experiential themes from textual transcription of 4 Registered Nurses

Commitment to Compassionate Care - Nurse S shared, "When I am with the patient, I immerse myself in the totality of patient care." Jean Watson's quotes on caring, "Transpersonal Presence beyond ego-physical phenomena is located within a (sacred) caring science context, beyond the physical alone; Unity Caring Science embraces human caring, evolving consciousness, Love and intentionality. Thus, authentic caring presence requires a unity awareness, which lies beyond the strictly physical presence" (WCSI, 2010). Nurse S spends caring moment with the realization that the patient is the most important being in that particular moment, putting in all her efforts, time, energy and attention, fully aware that compassionate care is what her patient needs.

Gratification in Action - Nurse D verbalized; "I have a feeling of satisfaction when I see that the patient loneliness subsides." Jean Watson's Caring Science described that in "practicing gratitude, we open our heart, allowing love and wonders and even more gratitude, energy and creativity, to flow through us and our experiences, perceptions and life events. Authentic Caritas Presence can be known only between two or more experiencing persons from their inner world in the moment" (WCSI, 2010). Watson further pronounced, "Any profession that loses its values becomes heartless; any profession that becomes heartless becomes soulless. Any profession that becomes heartless and soulless, becomes [Worthless]" (Watson, 2006).

Nurse D further expressed that, "Openness to patient's feelings through verbal and non-verbal expression can be a result of his positive outlook and experiences (taking care of different patients) consistently setting tone and creating an environment conducive to a caring relationship. Openness and positivity of Nurse D has transformed to a grateful heart, willing to continue to serve and care.

Patient and Compassionate Nurse equals Family- Nurse M expressed, "I felt fulfilled when the patient and family treats me as part of the family." Watson's caring science describes, "To engage in a transpersonal, caring-healing model involves transformation. A transpersonal self is a transformed self, beyond the ego self" (WCSI, 2010). The communication needs of the family and other supportive people depend on their role in the family system, age, decision-making ability, and other rules within a specific to the family. The involvement in patient care, may vary if family members also have multiple home and work responsibilities. Therefore, it may be a challenge for family members to be present at the bedside. Families may experience a high level of frustrations from the need for constant updating of information order to organize and prioritize other activities around their care giving role (Summer, 2006). At this moment, the presence of a nurse fulfilling the need of the patient and extending support to the family leads to patient and family recognizing the role of the nurse, appreciating the kindness and compassion, distinguishing the significant contribution of the nurse to the healing process and extending the relationship to other family members.

Cognitive Aspect of Care—Nurse C voiced, “When you are equipped with basic information to answer patient’s questions rapport is easy to establish.”

When the caring theory is integrated into the nursing curriculum, nursing students learn from early on in their practice to include the theory in their own practice, thereby allowing a more authentic experience of nursing for themselves and their patients (Nelson and Watson, 2012). The role of a nurse in imparting information is complex, because information must be provided within the appropriate context of education level, developmental level, stress level, and time constraints (Panopio, 2007). In this context, Caritas consciousness is described as the co-created relationship that promotes knowledge, growth, empowerment and healing processes and possibilities for patients and for the Nurse (Watson Caring Science Institute, 2010).

Putting together the experiential themes, the second reflection designates caring at the core, inner compass of care, nurturing begets belonging and confidence in knowing. Caring at the core, outlines the nurse’s qualities of having compassionate care and focuses on connecting with the patient. Confidence in knowing can be likened to the nurse’s preparation prior to actual interaction and in Watson’s words, “Intention of doing for another” (WCSI, 2010). Inner compass of care describes how the nurse honors human dignity. Nurturing begets belonging, shows that when the nurse engages in effective and loving communication, most of the time, patient and family acknowledge this behavior with appreciation.

The third reflection sums up the details into “Authentic Caring” and “Rapport as central to relationship.” This shows that the nurses are mindfully present. Watson’s caritas consciousness is being described as “open to connectedness with self, others, environment, universe while validating uniqueness of self and others in a trusting helping relationship around with loving kindness” (WCSI, 2010). Fundamental to establishing rapport is the development of a trusting relationship and the acknowledgement and appreciation of the patient and the family of the nurse’s presence. These experiences are consistent to the core concept of Watson’s theory on relational caring of self and others; transpersonal caring relationships; having caring occasions or moments (Watson, 2017). The gist of the lived experiences of SDMC nurses outlined that there is a caring moment. For a caring moment to occur the nurse needs to be mindfully present, acknowledges the patient and family with appreciation, focus on the totality or view the patient holistically and practicing gratitude to be able to continue to care unconditionally.

The symbolic representation of the lived experience of SDMC nurses in taking care of their patients depicts nurse’s hand touching the patient hand, stand still in caring moment (with mindful and caring presence, acknowledging patient holistically and a work commitment with gratitude).

Conclusion and Recommendation

The core of the lived experiences outlines that every caring moment is a product of human interaction. The value of a nurse centers on her being caring from moment to moment, hence; mindfully present, holistically compassionate and with a grateful heart.

The study involved 4 nurses only at St. Dominic Medical Center. Hence, its findings may not be generalizable to the entire population of nurses in the Philippines. However, its results could be utilized as a springboard for another follow up studies in caring moments years ahead.

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